

Image Bank: Guidelines for Photographers

Please be in contact with your onsite photography coordinator:

Name: _____

Email: _____

Background information:

RADx-UP is researching COVID-19 testing patterns in communities across the country and data on disparities in infection rates, disease progression and outcomes. RADx-UP is also developing strategies to reduce disparities in COVID-19 testing by supporting research projects across the country with established community partnerships.

RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) is led by the Duke Clinical Research Institute (DCRI) and the Center for Health Equity Research at UNC-Chapel Hill (UNC-CHER), in partnership with Community Campus Partnership for Health (CCPH). Our coordination of research project teams includes a wide range of education, training, implementation guidance, and facilitating connections.

[Click here to learn more about RADx-UP.](#)

Goals:

The RADx-UP Image Bank is a library of photos for RADx-UP research project teams to use in communications and recruitment materials. These photos are meant to reflect the diversity (racial/ethnic, gender, socioeconomic, ability, etc.) represented by the RADx-UP research projects as well as a variety of settings, both clinical and community-based.

Photography will be used for a variety of purposes and materials by both the RADx-UP CDCC and the 80+ research projects funded through RADx-UP. These could include, but are not limited to:

- Internal and external presentations
- Websites
- Fliers
- Health promotion materials
- Educational materials
- Social media campaigns
- Editorial materials
- Other communications materials

The RADx-UP CDCC hopes photos will allow RADx-UP research projects and their communities to feel seen by the materials we use because photos will reflect those served. The RADx-UP CDCC and other RADx-UP funded projects intend to use photos to support COVID-19 testing equity in our communities.

RADx-UP maintains the ownership and usage to all photos taken. Photos will be owned by the RADx-UP CDCC and they will be shared with RADx-UP funded research projects for their use, but will not be made available for public use.

These images will not be used for initiatives to generate income or sold for monetary gain.

Professional photographer selection:

RADx-UP research project teams have been chosen for professional photo shoots. Each research project that is participating in the Image Bank can choose their photographer. The CDCC also aims to engage community-based photographers who represent those served by RADx-UP. We hope that these photographers will be embedded in and represent the community that each research project works with.

The photography coordinator at each research project will schedule the “models” so that they are ready on your planned photo day. The CDCC provides consent forms for the coordinator to gather prior to the photo shoot. The coordinator must make sure that all consents are complete prior to the photography session. Individuals appearing in photos will receive monetary compensation (\$150 per person, up to 25 people per site).

Contracting with photographers:

Photographers will be set up as an individual contractor and must be approved through the UNC-Chapel Hill finance process. This could take several weeks to process.

Finance forms for photographers will be emailed to the photographer for completion.

RADx-UP will own all photos, but will allow research projects and community partners affiliated with RADx-UP to have access to use these photos for their communication needs. Photographers are not allowed to sell or use these photos.

We expect photo sessions to occur across a maximum of 8 hours. This may happen in one day or be spread over several. Here is a timeline outlining estimated dates for planning and completing the shoots. These dates are intended as a guideline only (for example, the shoots should take place around the end of March and beginning of April, but do not need to take place exactly on March 31st).

- Contracting process initiated: February 15
- Photo shoot scheduled: March 1
- "Model" sign-up finalized: March 15
- Photo shoot: March 31
- Incentives process initiated: April 15

Shot List:

Your photography coordinator will provide you with a shot list. We expect it will include community members, some staged clinical photos, and will highlight staff and volunteers that work for RADx-UP, etc.

Photo tags:

As you are reviewing your photos for upload to RADx-UP, you will be asked to tag them so that we can create a searchable repository. We will provide a final list at a later date, but this is an example of tags you might use:

<u>Family:</u>	<u>Clinical:</u>	<u>Individuals:</u>	<u>Geographic Locations:</u>	<u>Other:</u>
Multi-generation family	Testing Site	Elderly	Urban	Religious center
Multi-cultural Family	Clinical Staff	Youth	Rural	Community center
School age Children	Mobile Testing	Adults	Farming	Recreational
	Survey process	Differently-abled	School	Work setting

After the photo shoot:

After you have had an opportunity to choose your best photos, we ask that you review these photos with the research photography coordinator. This is an opportunity to make sure that all consents are accounted for and for the research photographer coordinator to ensure they fairly represent the organization. This is an important step with working with vulnerable populations.

Delivery of photos:

We will provide a link to a secure folder for you to upload your photos.

Acknowledgement:

Please sign below to acknowledge that have received, read, and understand this document.

Name

Date